

Evaluating Primary Responsibilities of Faculty Members with Faculty Performance Indicator Score Card (FPISC): An Academic Perspective of Pakistan

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Abstract

Evaluation of faculty members' performance in terms of their primary responsibilities is difficult, particularly when the contribution of faculty members is self-directed and uncoordinated. The model of scorecard is derived from the corporate sector, in which an organization identifies the key factors which are co-related with academia's mission. These factors are aligned then in accordance with the strategic importance, and every employee is set to evaluate as per the criteria of these factors. The process to correlate the principle responsibilities of faculty members with the University's mission has not previously been described. Thus, in this paper, the idea of scorecard has been applied to the academic environment, where key faculty performance competencies: Teaching competence, Research competence, and Service competence are set to evaluate in the perspective of the mission of academia. This study possesses qualitative nature, conducted through secondary data collection, including Job Descriptions, Teacher Evaluation Form, Higher Education Commission's Quality Assurance Manual, and other related documents. This scorecard has introduced a mechanism, which can evaluate the faculty members' performance in terms of their primary responsibilities in raw score. Using this scorecard, the competency of faculty members in their teaching, research, and service will separately be measured, which can reflect a clear picture of faculty member's performance in each of his/her primary responsibility and total score can determine when the score obtained against each of the responsibility will be accumulated. This scorecard is given name as, "Faculty Performance Indicator Score Card (FPISC)" that can be used to separately determine the strengthened and weak area of faculty members' performance in term of their primary responsibilities (Teaching, Research, and Service) in academia, which can certainly be helpful for Institute/Department, University to deliver the competency and productivity backed by the mission of academia.

Key Words: Primary Responsibilities; Faculty members, Performance Indicator; Scorecard.

I. INTRODUCTION

With time, the dynamics of higher education are changing. Today, the challenges for higher education to foster the knowledge economy are more than before. To overcome these challenges, the immediate requirements for the improvement in the field of faculty performance are inevitable. Due to increasing academic standards and the complexity of quality education, Universities/HEIs have focused their attention on a mechanism that can monitor, evaluate and measure the parameters of quality standards. In this regard, the role of faculty members highlights first. Faculty members are being held responsible to deliver the best standards and quality education in academia. According to their primary responsibilities, faculty members struggle to deliver tripartite duties: Teaching, Research, and Service. The deliverance competency of every faculty member in terms of his/her primary responsibilities considerably varies from faculty to faculty. Like, in the same department one faculty member is best in Teaching, but the other one from the same department is best in Research. The variation of skills between the faculty members performance, highlights the need of a mechanism which can separately evaluate faculty members' performance in terms of their primary responsibilities as well as highlight strengthened and weak area of their performance. Apart from this, the second flaw is about the unalignment of academia's mission with primary responsibilities of faculty members, which is not a simple matter. This study is particularly focused on the evaluation of faculty members' primary responsibilities (Teaching, Research, and Service) through the development of a faculty performance indicator scorecard that may measure their performance in the context of academia's mission.

II. SELECTION OF KEY RESPONSIBILITIES

In the perspective of study, the selection of key responsibilities was a basic step to simplify the complexity of the existing system. The selection of key responsibilities reflects the indicators which are major

contributors to their performance. For this reason, the first step in the development of performance indicator scorecard was to identify the indicators, which may be used to measure and evaluate faculty members' performance.

The faculty member of college and university undertake Research, Teaching, and Service as their role to conduct academic work of their respective Institutions (HAMRICK, 2020). The faculty of North Georgia University is responsible to carry the mission of the University in their Teaching, Scholarship, and Service. University of North Georgia expects from its faculty members that they should incorporate each of these responsibilities in their professional life on regular curriculum (Georgia, 2020). Faculty members of college and University have three traditional roles; Research, Teaching, and Service each role is impacted by considerable change, but teaching and research are most influenced by Technology (Hartman, 2007). Indiana University expects from its faculty members that they should abide by established policies for the smooth operation of academia's instructional programs. Every faculty member is responsible to deliver excellence in his/her professional activities through research, teaching, and Service (University, 2019). Faculty members at New York University are expected to meet their professional and institutional commitments at the University on regular basis. These commitments are regarding; time spent on teaching, research, student advising, clinical activities, and various kinds of University or outside professional service (University N. Y., 2020). The faculty members' role is to deliver the quality in Research, Teaching, and Service, so that the modern standards of Higher Education may be achieved with the deliverance of quality in the responsibilities of faculty members (University K. S., 2020). The individual role of faculty members is to support the mission of the university and respective departments. Furthermore, the university desires its faculty members' commitment to Teaching, Scholarly activities, and render public service (Pittsburgh, 2020). At University and HEI's faculty members shoulder the responsibility to carry the mission of higher education which they can achieve by delivering their quality potential in the field of research, teaching students, and applying their skills in the field of academic service (Ann E. Austin, 2017). Evaluating faculty members' performance in teaching, research, and service is a demand that grows out of government, the general public, and all sectors of the academic community (Associate, 2006).

Having the study of the aforementioned literature, it was simple to analyze the indicators which were to select as key indicators for the performance of faculty members. In every literature Teaching, Research, and Service are defined as primary responsibilities of faculty members. Thus, for this study Teaching, Research, and Service are selected as key performance indicators and the various aspects of said responsibilities are measured as performance deliverance of faculty members at university and HEI's.

III. DEVELOPING CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK LINKING MISSION STATEMENT AND KEY FACULTY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

Universities and Higher Education Institutes (HEIs) develop their mission statement to formulate their collective track. The mission statement of universities and HEIs determines the areas of importance to be focused upon, overall goal of academia, and action plan. The formulation of the mission statement considers benefiting internal and external stakeholders.

1) External Stakeholders

The external stakeholders of academia include:

- i. Government and Government backed advisory/regulatory authority or authorities
- ii. Industry: It refers to the entity who generally is not involved in any of the action of academia, but is a beneficiary of its product. This means the student and research work conducted by the academia has a direct impact upon the operations and development of Industry.
- iii. Society: The word society here refers the community or indigenous inhabitants who are benefited by the measures of academia.

2) Internal Stakeholders

The internal stakeholders refer to those who are the shortest beneficiaries of the actions of academia. The mission statement of academia also includes the benefits of internal stakeholders. The internal stakeholders of any academia could be:

- i. Faculty members
- ii. Students
- iii. Administration

Thus, by combining the primary responsibilities of faculty members with the mission of academia, this study has designed a conceptual framework (see figure: 1) that is set as the base for the development of Faculty Performance Indicating Score Card.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

IV. METHODOLOGY

This research is based on the qualitative approach of research, which is formulated on the basis of reviewing empirical evidences. Websites of multiple Universities, policy documents, research articles, and job descriptions of different Universities have been reviewed. By means of this review, the primary responsibilities of faculty members are evaluated, which are accustomed as key indicators and the same are linked with the needs and benefits of internal and external stakeholders of academia. The preferred result of this study includes, a list of key performance indicators, these indicators are formulated on a comprehensive conceptual framework which is a cornerstone of this study.

Figure 2: Research Methodology

V. CREATING FACULTY PERFORMANCE INDICATOR SCORE CARD (FPISC)

This research is based on two objectives. The first is to design a mechanism which can separately determine strengthen and weak area of faculty members' performance. The second objective is to align this mechanism with the mission of academia; so that, faculty members' performance may be measured on the scale of academic mission. In this regard, the first step was to highlight the key responsibilities of faculty members of colleges and Universities. In this process, the Job descriptions as well available policies related literature

of various universities were reviewed and the findings of review explored three fundamental criterions of faculty members, which are:

- 1) Teaching
- 2) Research
- 3) Service

1) Teaching

To develop a beneficial environment, it is essential for academia that it should put the teaching into practice as basic criteria of its performance. Effective teaching is an art that keeps students engaged in the process of learning and development. Effective teaching develops a healthy impact on the educational growth of students. The role of a faculty member cannot be restricted to theoretical teaching in the classroom but by their teaching in laboratories to deliver practical teaching as well as assess and evaluate the students learning in the classroom and at examination. Therefore, traits of teaching for assessment by scorecard include:

- i. Theory
- ii. Practical
- iii. Assessment and Evaluation

i. Theory:

As per literature, theory means, collection of facts on which practice of activities depend. Hereby this study, given traits of faculty members is selected to measure by score card:

- a. Lecture Expertise: Knowledge, skills and abilities of faculty members in their specialized subject are selected for measurement by score card, under the head “lecture preparation”.
- b. Completion of Course: In the beginning of every academic session, faculty members shoulder responsibility to design course outline which s/he has to teach during the academic session. Thus, for score card this responsibility of faculty members has been selected for assessment. Percentage of course covered by faculty member during academic session will be awarded as performance score.
- c. Standard of course aligning the need of Society, Industry and Government: To align academic mission with the primary responsibilities of faculty members is the second objective of this study. Therefore to meet said purpose, the quality of course designed by faculty members on the base of Societal, Industrial and Governmental needs be measured and faculty member may be rewarded score according to the compatibility of their designed course.

ii. Practical:

In the perspective of academic meaning, the practical means teaching by doing. The institution which teaches science and technology counts one additional credit hour for practical teaching. Therefore, this study has selected Practical teaching as a performance indicator of faculty members, which measures:

- a. Percentage (%) of Course exercised practically: This indicator is selected to assess the faculty members’ performance in completion of their course in the form of practical teaching. In this regard, the practical requirements of subject may compare with the faculty members’ actual performance and the score can be awarded accordingly.
- b. Practical Knowledge of Modern Technology: Being a faculty member, it counts as a trait that he/she possesses the good knowledge of modern practices and developments in terms of technologies linked with the subject s/he is specialized in. This indicator can be measured by departmental chair/competent authority after assessing faculty members’ practical knowledge and approach about standard technology aligning the needs of Industry and Government and award them score accordingly.
- c. Technology Used in Laboratory: In continuation with previous trait, this counts use of technology in Laboratories. This ensures the equipments used by faculty members in laboratory and same are aligned with standards of Government and Industry. The purpose of this trait is to equip students with the technology being used by the Industry or government. The performance measurement of this indicator is set on the disposal of Departmental Chair / competent authority.

iii. Assessment and Evaluation

Job description of every nomenclature of faculty members defines their role as assessor and evaluator. As per this sub indicator, faculty member is responsible to assess, evaluate, and measure students' performance in class room as well as in examination. Thus, this indicator has been incorporated in the score card which is further bifurcated in three more sub-indicators, which are:

- a. **Set Papers:** The Job Description of faculty member states setting paper as a role of their job. Therefore hereby this scorecard, such responsibility of faculty members is included as a factor of measurement. For this trait, the competent authority may award score to faculty members on the basis of the way they designs question papers as well as compares and contrast it with the syllabus taught during the session and draws a consequence which can be reflected in shape of score rewarded.
- b. **Assessment, Measurement and Evaluation of students in class, laboratory and Examination:** By this trait, the fairness of faculty members in assessment, measurement, and evaluation of students' performance will be the point to reward score by competent authority to faculty member.
- c. **Invigilation for Theory and Practical Examination:** As every Job Description counts invigilation in theoretical and practical examination as a duty of faculty members. Therefore, this study has set this factor as an indicator for measurement. This will reward score to faculty members on the base of their frequency of attendance as invigilator in practical as well as theoretical examinations.

Comprising all aforementioned performance indicators this score card for the assessment of faculty members' performance in teaching is designed as given in Table 1:

Table VV-1

TEACHING

Appraisal Factor	Sub-Appraisal Factor	Category	Score														
			10	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	0				
Teaching	THEORY	1	Lecture Preparation														
		2	Course Completion														
		3	Current Curriculum Standard (Course Competitiveness as per National/International Standards aligning the needs of Industry and Government)														
		4	Course updated Since _____														
	PRACTICAL	1	_____ % of Course exercised Practically														
		2	Practical Knowledge of Modern Technology														
		3	Technology used in lab is as per standards of Industry or Government. (Yes) OR (No) (If Yes then)														
	Assessment & Evaluation	1	Set Papers														
		2	Assessment, Measurement and Evaluation of students in class, Laboratory and Examination														
		3	Invigilation for Theory Examinations														
Total Score																	

2) Research

Following the teaching, research is defined as the primary responsibility of faculty members. During the review of policies of various universities, Research is observed as first responsibility of faculty members than teaching. Research on the whole, reflects faculty members' role as a scholar, who utilizes his/her skills, knowledge and potential in scholarly activities. In these days, every University and HEIs expects faculty members dedication to research, which is like an inherent component by universities. Therefore, it is important for every faculty member that s/he should actively participate in research activities. The approach of universities regarding research, varies from university to university. Hereby this study research is determined by two kinds which are:

i. **Research Publication**

ii. **Active Research**

i. Research Publication

Research publication refers the faculty members' contribution in research through articles, scientific research papers, books, monographs or any other original publication by which faculty members may communicate their scholarly outcome. Research publication is the basic on which faculty members are

assessed for their compensation like, promotion or tenure etc. Thus, the performance indicators which are selected to measure research publication are as follow:

a. Number of research paper published:

In Universities, as per the policy, faculty members are responsible to publish minimum one research paper in any national/international impact factor journal in a year; whereas no any limit is constrained for maximum publications by faculty members. As a result, there are some members who write multiple papers and others write just a paper in order to meet the requirement by the same time period. Thus, here in this score card it is particularly cited that each paper publication or presentation would be scored out separately. Whereas, the score for every paper will be awarded on the base of its publication in W, X, Y category journals. The competent authority may award maximum ten and minimum zero score for each publication or presentation. Means, the score earned will be in accordance to the number of publications or presentations by respective faculty members (More the publications, more will be the score and vice versa).

b. Article written in news papers, blogs etc:

Society and general public is external stake holder of Academia and for their awareness, it is mentioned in the job descriptions of faculty members that they may write down their articles in news papers, blogs, magazines or any other print or social media channel. Thus this score card has considered this effort of faculty member for score awarding. The procedure to award score in this regard would be same as it is for research publication.

c. Book Author:

Apart from articles, to author book or books is also a duty of faculty members, assigned to them by their job descriptions. Thus, here by this score card, this factor is also set to calculate. The score awarding procedure in this regard is also based on the quantity of number of books authored. The more number of books written the more will be score and vice versa.

ii. **Active Research**

Active research defines the fresh look within the specialized subject of faculty member. Active research possess the capacity to define the current issues in the perspective of academia, industry, government or community. It delivers the solutions to current problems, exploring future opportunities, threats and suggests the ways to utilize opportunities and tackle with threats. Hereby this score card, the active research determines:

- Identification of fresh areas of research within the field of specialization of faculty member by aligning the needs of academia, industry and government.
- Supervising research scholars
- Monitoring of research projects
- Draft reports about the progress of research projects
- Leader or member of the team of researchers for any specific research.

Table 2

RESEARCH

Appraisal Factor	Sub-Appraisal Factor	Category	Score										
			10	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	0
Research	Publication	1	_____ Research paper published/presented during the year as first or single author in International, Asian, and National academic journals.										
		Paper 01	Topic _____										
		Paper 02	Topic _____										
		Paper 03	Topic _____										
		2	_____ Research paper published during the year as co-author or 3 rd author with professionals of Academia, Industry, Government or others in International, Asian, and National academic journals.										
		Paper 01	Topic _____										
		Paper 02	Topic _____										
		Paper 03	Topic _____										
		3	Authorship										
		a	Book Author										

		b	Written Articles in newspapers and magazines, Linked in, Google Scholar and other blogs. (for the popularization of Science and Technology and Development on the trends adopted by Industry and Government).																	
Active	1		Fresh areas of research identified within specialist subject areas according to the need of Industry or Government. (Yes) OR (No) (If Yes then)																	
	2		Supervision of undergraduate, Postgraduate (Master) and PhD Students.																	
	3		Monitoring progress on large research projects																	
	4		Written reports to relevant bodies about progress of research																	
	5		Lead team of researchers																	
			Total Score																	

3) Service

Apparently, service means, productive participation of faculty members in the internal and external activities by investing their skills, knowledge, and abilities for the promotion and achievement of academic mission. According to job Description and literature about faculty members duties and responsibilities. In the perspective of academia, service is bifurcated into two kinds which are:

- i. Internal service
- ii. External Service

i. Internal Service

Internal service means faculty members' participation on the extra curriculum and research activities for department or academia. When academia initiates decision regarding promotion, and tenure there service plays a major role. At that time, the list of faculty members participation in committees or task forces reflects the role and importance of faculty member to institution. The longer the list, the greater the role is considered. Thus, by this score card service evaluates:

a. Academic Planning :

This reveals the faculty members' role as an academic planner. According to this, foresightness for academic planning, introduce new degree programs, and participation for the development of curriculum can be measured. This role is subject to the nomination of faculty member as academic planner and the performance will be assessed in that case only.

b. Committee Work :

This responsibility is also the subject to faculty members' nomination/allocation for any committee or task force. More the committee or task force participation more will be the score and vice versa.

c. Administrative Work: This indicator is specified with the purpose to evaluate the quality of administrative ability. Hereby this score card, the components which are set to spot light faculty members' administrative capacities are:

- Communication
- Team work
- Decision making
- Problem Solving
- Risk Analysis

In this connection, faculty members' ability in each of the trait will be measured separately and score would also be awarded separately according to their skills and abilities in each of the trait.

d. Student Counseling:

Most institutes count student advising as a role of academic members' service (Associate, 2006). Keeping in view aforesaid notion, in this score card, this trait has been included. As per this component faculty member is responsible to utilize their knowledge and ability for emotional, social and academic counseling of students. Hence, such components are included in the score card as factors to measure faculty members' role as student counselor.

e. Student Discipline :

Managing students' behaviour by handling their challenging behaviour is a complicated responsibility of faculty members. Student Discipline, represents the technical and social skills. Means, faculty members' ability to treat students who are from different backgrounds, with different experiences and intellectuality is the subject of significance. Thus, due to the importance of this indicator it has been included for measurement in scorecard.

f. Any other Responsibility :

This is conditional evaluation, in which if faculty member is assigned any additional responsibility which is beyond the indicators listed above in the service of faculty member then s/he will be awarded additional score. This responsibility is also a subject to measure in raw score.

ii. External Service

External Service means faculty members' service for external stakeholders. Here by this score card the faculty members' participation in professional organizations related with science, technology and development will be measured, with the title as Professional Contribution. The sample score card for the assessment of faculty service is as given in Table 3:

Table 3

SERVICE

Appraisal Factor	Sub-Appraisal Factor	Category	Score																
			10	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	0						
	External Service																		
Service	Professional Contribution	Participation in professional Organizations of Science and Technology. (Yes) OR (No) (If Yes then)																	
		Participation in various Civic groups (Yes) OR (No) (If Yes then)																	
		Participation in government and non-government Organizations and Industry (Yes) OR (No) (If Yes then)																	
		Internal Service																	
	Academic Planning	Participation for the development of curriculum programs																	
		Foresightedness for academic planning																	
		Design new academic/degree programs																	
	Committee Work	Member/Convener _____ Committee																	
		Member/Head of _____ Task Force																	
	Administrative Work	Communication																	
		Teamwork																	
		Decision making																	
		Problem solving																	
	Student Counseling	Risk Identification and ability to handle																	
		Academic Counseling																	
Student Discipline	Social and emotional Counseling																		
	Managing student groups or																		
Any other Responsibility	Any task or assignment performed during the year. (Yes) OR (No) (If Yes then)																		
		Total Score																	

4. Total Obtained Score

The total obtained score is the table that is included in this score card. The purpose of this table is to spotlight over all accumulated score of faculty members, which are separately measured. The formula to calculate total obtained score is:

$$\text{Total Obtained Score} = \text{Teaching Score} + \text{Research score} + \text{Service Score}$$

Table 4

Appraisal Factor	Minimum Score	Obtained Score
Teaching		
Research		
Services		
Total Obtained Score		

5. Placement of Score Card

Faculty Performance Indicator Score Card (FPISC), may be outright at the time of Annual Confidential Report (ACR) or at the end of academic year. This scorecard may also be included as a complementary part of Annual Confidential Report (ACR). The purpose of this score card is to assess faculty members' academic responsibilities by following the mission of academia. The consistent performance evaluation through FPISC, can bring long term comparison of faculty members' performance by highlighting their strengths, weaknesses and improvement in performance regarding their primary responsibilities.

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